

[Nunzia Di Rienzo – Published online on May 15, 2025]

The Treasures of Syriac... Gaze ܩܙܐ

A Podcast to discover the Syriac world

On May 1st, 2025 the first episode of the podcast *Gaze* was released.

Gaze – The Treasures of Syriac it is one of the outcomes of the Marie Skłodowska Curie project ForM-Forged Memories.

The title of the podcast plays with the meaning of the Syriac word “gaze” (ܩܙܐ in Syriac script) meaning “treasures”, and the English verb “gaze”.

So, a deep look at the treasures of an often underestimated culture.

Gaze – The Treasures of Syriac is an attempt to introduce the Syriac world and traditions to anyone who is curious about it. Scientific accuracy and simple, straightforward language are the main characteristics *Gaze* seeks to achieve.

Nunzia Di Rienzo (La Sapienza University of Rome) and Jeanne-Nicole Mellon Saint-Laurent (Marquette University) dialogue on the Syriac traditions and major themes, interacting with their guests from the academic world.

The podcast is not intended to academics or specialists: it is for those people who are unfamiliar with and curious about this fascinating world.

Gaze is currently hosted by Marquette University in Milwaukee, WI.

The first two episodes – a general introduction to the Syriac world and a virtual journey to the city of Edessa – are online.

The next ones will come out on May 29 and June 12, and so on, every two weeks.

The podcast is available on Spotify, Apple Podcast and Amazon Music.